

Table 1: Identified sources

Title	Overview	Font type	Reference
The Belmont Report, ethical principles and guidelines for the protection of human subjects of research	Ethical factors in research involving humans	Code of Ethics	[12]
Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI: high-level expert group on artificial intelligence	Ethical factors in AI	Code of Ethics	[7]
Ethically aligned design: A vision for Prioritizing Human Well-being with Autonomous and Intelligence Systems	Ethical factors in AI	Code of Ethics	[13]
ACM Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct	Ethical factors for professionals	Code of Ethics	[2]
Code of Ethics for IT professionals	Ethical factors for professionals	Code of Ethics	[21]
New Zealand Computer Society (NZCS) code of ethics and professional conduct	Ethical factors for professionals	Code of Ethics	[1]
Software Engineering code of ethics	Ethical factors for professionals	Code of Ethics	[9]
Ethical considerations in case studies	Ethical principles for case study	Research Paper	[28]
Guidelines for conducting and reporting case study research in software engineering	Ethical issues for case study	Research Paper	[19]
A Roadmap for Ethics-Aware Software Engineering	Framework for integrating ethical considerations in SE	Research Paper	[3]
Notifying and Involving Users in Experimentation: Ethical Perceptions of Software Practitioners	Ethical issues in software experimentation	Research Paper	[27]
Ethical Interviews in Software Engineering	Important Ethical Factors for SE Interviews	Research Paper	[24]
Ethical Issues in Empirical Studies of Software Engineering	Ethical factors in empirical studies in SE	Research Paper	[23]
“This is Just a Prototype”: How Ethics Are Ignored in Software Startup-Like Environments	Neglected ethical factors in software startups	Research Paper	[26]
Implementing AI Ethics in Practice: An Empirical Evaluation of the RESOLVEDD Strategy	Ethical factors in AI	Research Paper	[25]
Exploring Ethical Requirements Elicitation for Applications in the Context of AI	Ethical factors in AI application requirements extraction	Research Paper	[6]
The ethics of online research with unsuspecting users: From A/B testing to C/D experimentation	Factors and ethical issues in online experimentation	Research Paper	[5]
The Ethics of AI Ethics: An evaluation of guidelines	Ethical factors in AI	Research Paper	[10]
How to Write Ethical User Stories? Impacts of the ECCOLA Method	Ethical factors in agile software development	Research Paper	[11]
Ethical Guidelines for Solving Ethical Issues and Developing AI Systems	Ethical factors in AI	Research Paper	[4]
Towards a Taxonomy of Ethical Considerations in Crowdsourcing	Ethical factors in crowdsourcing	Research Paper	[14]
The Ethics of Online Controlled Experiments (A/B Testing)	Factors and ethical issues in online experimentation	Research Paper	[18]
Ethics in the Age of Disruptive Technologies: An Operational Roadmap	Factors and ethical issues for establishing and maintaining a Responsible Technology Management System	Research Paper	[8]
Artificial intelligence ethics guidelines for developers and users: clarifying their content and normative implications	Ethical factors and issues in AI	Research Paper	[20]
Trustworthy Online Controlled Experiments: A Practical Guide to A/B Testing	Issues and solutions for ethics in online experiments	Research Paper	[15]
Continuous Experimentation Cookbook: An introduction to systematic experimentation for software-intensive businesses	Issues and solutions for ethics in online experiments	Research Paper	[17]
Guidelines for using financial incentives in software-engineering experimentation	Issues and solutions for financial incentives in SE	Research Paper	[16]